

1 **Unbiased discovery of genes required for pluripotency: ERBB2.**

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6 Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency
7 as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the
8 multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and
9 embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We
10 describe identification of ERBB2 as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in human
11 embryonic stem cells.

12 Citations

13 1. Wang, X., Sun, Y., Wong, J. and Conklin, D., 2013. PPAR γ maintains ERBB2-positive breast
14 cancer stem cells. *Oncogene*, 32(49), pp.5512-5521.

15 2. Wang, L., Schulz, T.C., Sherrer, E.S., Dauphin, D.S., Shin, S., Nelson, A.M., Ware, C.B., Zhan, M.,
16 Song, C.Z., Chen, X. and Brimble, S.N., 2007. Self-renewal of human embryonic stem cells requires
17 insulin-like growth factor-1 receptor and ERBB2 receptor signaling. *Blood, The Journal of the American*
18 *Society of Hematology*, 110(12), pp.4111-4119.